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Doctors in the Italian Regions

They increased by an average of 10.20% in the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022.

ISTAT calculates the number of doctors in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants. The data refer to the period from 2012 to 2022.

Doctors in the Italian regions in 2022. The analysis of data on the number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants in the Italian regions in 2022 shows significant regional variability that reflects not only the geographical and demographic diversity of the country but also inequalities in access to medical care. Particularly evident is the contrast between regions like Lazio and Sardinia, which boast the highest number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants, suggesting better availability of healthcare services, and regions like Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol and Basilicata, which are at the other end of the spectrum, potentially indicating greater challenges in accessing care. These inequalities among the regions raise important questions about equity in access to healthcare services, emphasizing the need for regional health policies aimed at ensuring a more equitable distribution of medical resources. It is essential that such policies not only aim to increase the number of doctors in areas with shortages but also improve the efficiency and accessibility of healthcare services, to guarantee all Italian citizens access to high-quality care regardless of their region of residence.

Doctors in the Italian regions from 2012 to 2022. The analysis of data on doctors in the Italian regions shows a general trend of both absolute and percentage increases in the number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants from 2012 to 2022. The absolute variation, which represents the change in the number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants, highlights increases in all regions except Calabria, where the number of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants remained unchanged. From a percentage point of view, Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol shows the most significant increase with a rise of 16.67%, followed by Veneto and Emilia-Romagna with increases of 15.63% and 15.00%, respectively. These data suggest an improvement in access to medical care in these regions, probably reflecting investments in the healthcare sector or demographic changes. Conversely, the regions with the lowest percentage changes are Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste and Basilicata, with increases of 2.78% and 2.94%, respectively, suggesting much more moderate growth in the availability of doctors. This might reflect stability in the demand for medical services or challenges in attracting new doctors to these regions. Calabria is the only region with no change in the doctor-to-population ratio, indicating a possible stagnation in the regional healthcare sector that might require attention to ensure that access to medical care does not deteriorate. The data reflect an overall improvement in access to medical care in Italy, with regional variations suggesting differences in the growth rate of the healthcare sector

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influenced by demographic factors, healthcare investment policies, and the ability to attract medical professionals to different regions.

Doctors in the Italian macro-regions from 2012 to 2022. The average density of doctors in Italy increased from 3.8 to 4.2 doctors per 1,000 inhabitants from 2012 to 2022, with an absolute variation of 0.4 and a percentage growth of 10.53%. This indicates a general improvement in access to medical care at the national level. There is variation in both the initial density (2012) and the final density (2022) among the regions, indicating disparities in access to medical care depending on the location. The North-East shows the highest percentage growth (13.89%), while the Mezzogiorno shows the lowest (7.69%). The North-South divide, a recurring theme in discussions about Italy, persists in the medical sector, although improvements are observed in all areas. Southern regions start from a lower density and, despite increases, remain behind compared to northern and central regions. The density of doctors has uniformly grown but with a marked difference in the North-East, which surpasses other northern sub-regions in percentage growth. This might reflect targeted regional health policies or particular demographic dynamics. The Center starts from a strong position with the highest initial density (4.3) and maintains robust percentage growth, indicating a good capacity to attract or train medical staff. The Mezzogiorno, South, and Islands show more modest increases, with the Islands presenting the highest growth rate among the three. This raises questions about equity in the distribution of healthcare resources and the mobility of medical professionals. The increase in doctor density is a positive indicator for access to healthcare, but regional disparities underline the need for policies aimed at reducing the North-South gap. The growth, though positive, might still not be sufficient to meet the increasing demand, especially considering the aging Italian population. Focused investments might be necessary. The variation in growth among the regions might also reflect internal mobility trends of doctors, with professionals moving to areas with better opportunities or working conditions.

North-South Divide. The analysis of data on the density of doctors per 1,000 inhabitants in the various Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022 provides evidence of a divide between the North and the South. While the northern and central regions have shown a significant increase in doctor density, with the North-East registering the highest percentage growth (13.89%) and the Center starting from an initially high density (4.3 per 1,000 inhabitants in 2012), the regions of the Mezzogiorno, South, and Islands present more modest increases. In particular, the Mezzogiorno records the lowest percentage growth (7.69%), indicating a divergence in the ability to attract or train qualified medical staff. This might reflect differences in terms of investments in the healthcare sector, professional opportunities, and quality of life, which tend to favor northern and central regions over southern and insular ones. This discrepancy in the growth of medical density is a concrete expression of the North-South divide, highlighting how disparities extend beyond the economic sphere to include the quality and accessibility of healthcare. Although there is a general improvement in doctor density at the national level, regional differences remain marked, underscoring the need for targeted policies to address and reduce these inequalities, ensuring equitable and universal access to healthcare throughout Italy.

Conclusions. The number of doctors increased on average by 10.20% in the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022. The macro-region with the highest level of doctors is the Center, followed by the Islands, the Mezzogiorno, and the North-East. However, between 2012 and 2022, the percentage of doctors grew mainly in the central-northern regions with more contained values in the southern

regions. To address the challenge of increasing the number of doctors, a government can adopt a range of political and economic strategies targeting different aspects of the medical education and professional pathway. Firstly, investments in medical education are crucial: by increasing funding for universities and medical schools, admission capacity can be expanded and the quality of education enhanced. This would be central in the diagram, with direct connections to student incentive strategies and improvements in educational infrastructure. Simultaneously, the introduction of economic incentives for medical students, such as scholarships, tuition fee reductions, and favorable loans, can stimulate enrollment in medical courses. These incentives can be particularly effective if tied to commitments to work in areas with a shortage of doctors, creating a virtuous cycle between education and territorial needs. At the same time, improving working conditions for already practicing doctors, through salary increases and strengthening working conditions, aims to make the profession more attractive and reduce the dropout rate. This policy connects directly to the quality of life of doctors and the healthcare system's ability to retain talent. The international training and recruitment of doctors, facilitating the entry and employment in the country of professionals trained abroad and simplifying the qualification recognition processes, opens the healthcare system to a global talent pool. This strategy can help quickly fill existing gaps, especially in critical areas or specializations with shortages. Finally, investments in advanced healthcare technologies can make medical practice more efficient and less burdensome, reducing workload and increasing the attractiveness of the profession. The adoption of such technologies can improve the quality of care and professional satisfaction, attract new doctors, and retain existing ones.

Declarations

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Appendix

